

Influence of Firm Financial Characteristics on Leverage in Automobile and Accessories Companies Listed in Nairobi Securities Exchange

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Abstract

Capital market is supposed to be the source of finances but in Africa, liquidity problems have inhibited this role. Statistically, most securities exchanges in Africa are low with the highest liquidity recorded in Africa being from Egypt at 37.9% and the third highest Khartoum Stock Exchange at 32.5%. Hence, the current evaluated the influence of firm financial characteristics on the leverage of the listed automobile and accessories firm in Nairobi securities exchange. Study findings revealed the positive moderating effect of operating cash flows on the influence of firm financial characteristics on the leverage of listed automobile and accessories companies in Nairobi securities exchange.

Key Words: *Financial characteristics, Firm size, Profitability, Tangibility, Growth opportunities*

Introduction

Capital market is supposed to be the source of finances but in Africa, liquidity problems have inhibited this role. Statistically, most securities exchanges in Africa are low with the highest liquidity recorded in Africa being from Egypt at 37.9% and the third highest Khartoum Stock Exchange at 32.5% (ASEA, 2013). These liquidity problems are attributed to a few listings, low levels of retail investors, holding of huge funds in pension's funds and low adoption of technology based trading platforms (ASEA, 2015).

There has been a continued metamorphosis from informal, manual to the automated trading system at Nairobi securities exchange. In 1954 NSE was constituted as a voluntary association of stockbrokers under societies Act (NSE, 2016). After the privatization of Kenya Commercial Bank in 1988, NSE has grown in leaps and bounds in its trading volume. The market capitalization has increased to beyond Kshs. 2.2 trillion with 68 firms listed in 12 heterogeneous market segments (NSE, 2016). Further, 20 NSE share index has exceeded 5000 points which can be perceived as huge capital mobilization. The bond market has also been an upward trend at more than Kshs 500 billion (NSE, 2016).

Bereznicka (2013) investigated the causal relationship between asset structure and capital structure amongst companies operating in the European Union. Through, use of secondary data for periods from 2000 to 2010, correlation analysis revealed a negative and significant relationship between current assets ratio and long-term liabilities. However, a positive relationship between current asset ratio and total debt was observed. They found a strong positive relationship between the current assets and short-term debt. The findings are consistent with the maturity matching principle.

Abdullah, Parvez, Karim and Tooheen (2015) investigated the impact of financial leverage and market size on stock return on selected manufacturing companies listed in Dhaka securities exchange. Regression analysis was used to analyze five-year data drawn from annual financial statements in periods from 2008 to 2012. Results of the study revealed an inverse relationship between stock return and financial leverage while market size had a positive relationship. Their results were in support of signaling and pecking theory since a company utilize borrowed finances to signal low chances of retaining the profit earned.

Padaya (2016) investigated the impact of financial leverage on market value added on a sample of 197 companies which were listed in Bombay stock exchange in a five-year period from 2010 to 2014. Both univariate and multivariate analysis revealed a positive and significant relationship between financial leverage and market value added. The study findings mirrored signaling theory since a company attracting debt financing ought to be in a position to service its debts and has low signals of financial distress and bankruptcy.

A Jordanian study to examine the effect of financial leverage, growth, firm size and profitability was carried out by AlGhusin (2015). Purposive sampling approach was adopted to select 10 companies which were actively

trading from 1995 to 2005. Through regression and correlation analysis results of the study revealed positive and significant effect between financial leverage, growth, and profitability. This implies that for a financial to attain superior growth then it should borrow and invest the funds in most profitable investment opportunities. Although, the data was a panel in nature the study did not carry out diagnostic tests such as normality, stationarity and granger causality and these would have guided the choice of the most appropriate model to fit the data. Consequently, the study sought:

- i. To determine the influence of tangibility of assets on the leverage of automobile and accessories firms listed at Nairobi Securities Exchange.
- ii. To find out the influence of growth opportunities on the leverage of automobile and accessories listed firms at Nairobi Securities Exchange.
- iii. To establish the influence of firm size on the leverage of automobile and accessories firms listed at Nairobi Securities Exchange.
- iv. To examine the influence of profitability on the leverage of automobile and accessories firms listed at Nairobi Securities Exchange.
- v. To evaluate the moderating effect of operating cash flows on the influence of financial characteristics on the leverage of automobile and accessories firms listed at Nairobi Securities Exchange.

Literature Review

Modigliani and Miller (1958) demonstrated that in a fully efficient market in which there are no taxes, transactions or bankruptcy costs and that there is abundant information at the disposal of all parties. The value of the firm is not dependent on leverage because every firm's investment decision is solely dependent on the choice of its asset class. To attain financing optimality then a balance between interest costs and floatation cost associated with issuing new debt. Further, they purported that profitability and risk are firm value determinants and not capital structure. Indeed, the investment decision is mainly determined by the arbitrage opportunities which exist in any viable investment opportunity. Therefore, investors will tend to dispose of the share of highly valued entities and invest in underpriced companies (Mwangi, 2016).

Due to investors' rationality behaviour, Modigliani and Miller (1958) purported that there exists an inverse relationship between the cost of equity and gearing ratio and the investors are unwilling to take any risk which they cannot be compensated. In case when the tax rate is zero, then it will be hard for any firm to obtain optimal capital structure. Further, Alifani and Nugroho (2013) argued that there are high chances of using debt financing because of the advantages associated with corporate taxes.

The theory is not void of criticism more so because of the assumptions in which the theory is based on. In fact, it is so hard to have an operation environment void of transaction costs, bankruptcy costs and agency conflicts (Luigi & Sorin, 2009; Mwangi, 2016). The theory is appropriate for the study because there is a need to evaluate the value of the firm in regard to financing choice. Indeed, an increase in book value to market ratio of listed companies may trigger an increase in firm value and consequently enhance the firm's ability to borrow. From the foregoing literature review, the following relationship was conceptualized.

Methodology

The study used panel data. Panel data is a series of multidimensional data where the behaviour of entities are observed over time (Wooldridge, 2002). The key advantage of panel data is the ability to allow the researcher to control for variables that are not observable or measurable like culture and management practices over time but not across entities (Wooldridge, 2002). It was obtained from the NSE handbooks and from specific companies’ websites. As shown in the data collection sheet data on non-current assets, market prices, book value, turnover, total liabilities, profit after tax, operating cash flows were gathered. Secondary data was collected for period 2008-2016. Univariate and multivariate techniques were applied for data analysis. The influence was tested through the use of regression analysis and moderation was examined through an examination of marginal changes of slope coefficients due to the introduction of operating cash flows. The general models were of the form:

$$L_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 T_{i,t} + \beta_2 S_{i,t} + \beta_3 G_{i,t} + \beta_4 P_{i,t} + \epsilon_j \dots \dots \dots \text{Model 1}$$

The following regression model with the moderating variable was used for the analysis as proposed by Baron and Kenny (1986).

$$L_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 T_{i,t} + \beta_2 S_{i,t} + \beta_3 G_{i,t} + \beta_4 P_{i,t} + \beta_5 CF_{i,t} + CF_{i,t}(\beta_6 T_{i,t} + \beta_7 S_{i,t} + \beta_8 G_{i,t} + \beta_9 P_{i,t}) + \epsilon_j \dots \dots \dots \text{Model 2}$$

Where

L_{it} - total liabilities/total assets for each firm i at time t

T = Tangibility of assets, G =Growth opportunities, S =Firm size, P = Profitability, CF =Operating cash flows, β_i ($i=0,1,2,\dots,9$) are the associated regression coefficients, ϵ_j is the associated error term.

Findings and Discussions

Descriptive Statistics for Automobile and Accessories

As shown in Table 4.3, the average tangibility for listed automobile and allied companies was 47% with a minimum of 16% and 87%. Skewness coefficient 0.32 units revealed that companies quoted in this sector have skewed asset tangibility. Profitability in automobile and allied sector averaged at -0.01, this showed that most companies were incurring losses within the period under investigation. The minimum profitability was -0.31 and a maximum of 0.16. Skewness coefficient of -1.45 confirmed that most companies were loss making.

Average firm size was 13.72, with minimum 11.30 and maximum of 16.36. There was minimum variation in firm size and all firms had an almost similar size. Average firm growth was 0.64, with a maximum of 2.29 units and a minimum growth of 0.00. Skewness coefficient was 1.66, this implied that the growth opportunities were not normally distributed. Average operating cash flows was 0.13, with a maximum of 3.46 and a minimum of -2.46. This shows that there was a wide variation in operating cash flows. For every shilling generated in automobile 13 cents were incurred on operating expenses. Negative skewness indicated that most of the quoted companies in automobile and accessories were dependent on supplies mercy. This calls for an evaluation of quoted companies operating procedures to optimize with operational costs.

The average long-term average was 9%, with a maximum of 38% and a minimum of 0%. The average skewness coefficient was 1.97, this implied that leverage was not normally distributed. Average short-term debt to total assets was 52%, with a minimum of 31% and a maximum of 62%. Short term debt was negative; this implies that most of the companies in this sector were highly financed using short term debt. The average total debt to total assets was 60%, the maximum total debt to total assets was 88% and a minimum of 31%. There was minimal variation as accounted for by 11% and skewness coefficient of -0.05.

Table 1 Descriptive Statistics for Automobile and Accessories

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation	Skewness	
	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Std. Error
T	22	0.16	0.87	0.47	0.23	0.32	0.49
P	22	-0.31	0.16	-0.01	0.12	-1.45	0.49
S	22	11.30	16.36	13.72	1.82	0.36	0.49
G	21	0.00	2.29	0.64	0.55	1.66	0.50
CF	22	-2.28	3.46	0.13	1.19	0.61	0.49
LTA	22	0.00	0.38	0.09	0.11	1.97	0.49
STA	22	0.31	0.62	0.52	0.07	-1.19	0.49
DTA	22	0.31	0.88	0.60	0.11	-0.05	0.49

Autocorrelation for Automobile and Accessories Companies Listed in Nairobi Securities Exchange

As shown in Table 2, models with LTA as the response variable had F statistics of 4.57, without cash flow moderation, and 24.683 with moderation. The p values for both were greater than 0.05. The model without moderation where STA is the response variable had an F statistic of 0.815 with a p value of 0.4620 and model with moderation had an F statistic of 13.032 and p value of 0.0689 to indicate non-significance at 5% significance level. This implied absence of first order serial correlation. For the DTA response variable models, the F statistics were 798.695 and 106.893 with p values of 0.0012 and 0.0092 without and with moderation respectively. This, therefore, implies the presence of serial correlation. With the presence of the first order, serial correlation FGLS models were fitted.

Table 2 Wooldridge Test for Automobile and Accessories Companies Listed in Nairobi Securities Exchange

Dependent variable	Model	F (1,2)	Prob>F
LTA	Without moderator	4.57	0.166
	With moderator	24.683	0.382
STA	Without moderator	0.815	0.4620
	With moderator	13.032	0.0689
DTA	Without moderator	798.695	0.0012
	With moderator	106.893	0.0092

Multicollinearity Test Statistics for Automobile and Accessories Listed Companies in Nairobi Securities Exchange

Table 3 presents the VIFs for the various study variables. The results indicate that the VIFs, we not greater than 5 hence there was no collinearity amongst independent variables (Gujarati, 2003).

Table 3 Multicollinearity Test Statistics for Automobile and Accessories Listed Companies in Nairobi Securities Exchange

Variable	VIF	1/VIF
T	9.87	0.101358
S	6.84	0.14623
CF	3.65	0.273921
G	1.57	0.637146
P	1.31	0.763919
Mean VIF	4.65	

Heteroskedasticity Test Results for Automobile and Accessories Listed Companies in Nairobi Securities Exchange

Table 4 shows the likelihood ratio tests statistics for automobile and accessories companies listed in NSE. The null hypotheses of the tests were that the error variance was homoscedastic for each model. The likelihood-ratio tests produced chi-square values of 28.3, 5.25 and 6.56 with p-values of 0.0000, 0.3865 and 0.2554. This implies that the test was significant at 5% level of significance hence the existence of heteroscedasticity in the study. To remedy the problem, FGLS estimation technique was used (Wooldridge, 2002).

Table 4 Heteroskedasticity Test Results for Automobile and Accessories Listed Companies in Nairobi Securities Exchange

Response Variable's models	Chi Square	Degree of freedom	P value
STA	28.3	5	0.000
LTA	5.25	5	0.3865
DTA	6.56	5	0.2554

Stationarity Test Results for Automobile and Accessories Companies Listed in Nairobi Securities Exchange

The unit root test statistics for companies listed in the automobile and accessories sector in NSE are presented in Table 5. From the table, it is evident that all variables are stationary at the level since the null hypothesis that all variables are not stationary at 5% significant level is rejected. This is further assurance on the robustness of the expected results. Further on, there was no need to differentiate the data.

Table 5 Stationarity Test Results for Automobile and Accessories Companies Listed in Nairobi Securities Exchange

Variable	Statistic	Value	p-value	
T	Inverse chi-squared(84)	P	26.2445	0.000
	Inverse normal	Z	2.495	0.000
	Inverse logit t(199)	L*	3.7076	0.000
	Modified inv. chi-squared	Pm	6.0706	0.000
P	Inverse chi-squared(84)	P	25.0228	0.000
	Inverse normal	Z	-2.1678	0.015
	Inverse logit t(199)	L*	-3.4269	0.001
	Modified inv. chi-squared	Pm	5.4914	0.000
G	Inverse chi-squared(84)	P	75.8478	0.000
	Inverse normal	Z	-4.5884	0.000
	Inverse logit t(194)	L*	-11.6992	0.000

CF	Modified inv. chi-squared	Pm	20.1633	0.000
	Inverse chi-squared(78)	P	33.9642	0.000
	Inverse normal	Z	3.4962	0.000
	Inverse logit t(199)	L*	3.5052	0.000
S	Modified inv. chi-squared	Pm	-5.0877	0.000
	Inverse chi-squared(78)	P	33.687	0.000
	Inverse normal	Z	3.5108	0.000
	Inverse logit t(199)	L*	3.5003	0.000
	Modified inv. chi-squared	Pm	-6.677	0.000

Hausman Test Statistics for Automobile and Allied Companies Listed in Nairobi Securities Exchange

As shown in Tables 6 for LTA, for STA and for DTA models with and without moderation, the nulls were not rejected at 5% risk level since the p values were (greater than 0.05) 0.1645, 0.1552, 0.0972, 0.4791, 0.6942 and 0.3868 respectively. Hence the most appropriate models for them were random effects.

Table 6 Hausman Test Statistics for Automobile and Allied Companies Listed in Nairobi Securities Exchange

Dependent variable	Model	Chi Square	df	P value
LTA	Without moderator	3.61	2	0.1645
	With moderator	3.73	2	0.1552
STA	Without moderator	4.66	2	0.0972
	With moderator	1.47	2	0.4791
DTA	Without moderator	0.73	2	0.6942
	With moderator	1.9	2	0.3868

Granger Causality Test Results for Automobile and Accessories Companies Listed in Nairobi Securities Exchange

As shown in Table 7, the p-values for all lagged financial characteristics (in isolation) values and DTA, run against DTA, are greater than 5% level of significance. This implies that the null hypotheses that individual financial characteristic does not granger cause leverage are not rejected for automobile and accessories listed companies in NSE. When all lagged values of financial characteristics and DTA were run against DTA at the same time, the p value was zero. Being less than 5% level of significance, it means that the null hypothesis that financial characteristics do not granger causes leverage is rejected. It means that the financial characteristics of a firm, as a combination but not in isolation, can explain its leverage.

When the lagged values of DTA and individual financial characteristic were run against individual financial characteristics values at the same time, the p value for T and G were less than 5% level of significance. The p values for S and P were greater than the said significance level. This implies that for T and G, the null hypotheses that leverage does not granger cause tangibility and growth are rejected at a 5% significance level.

Table 7 Granger Causality Test Results for Automobile and Accessories Companies Listed in Nairobi Securities Exchange

Dependent	Independent (Lagged)	F Statistic	P value
DTA	S,DTA	0.64	0.6103
	T,DTA	2.48	0.3071
	P,DTA	2.04	0.3643
	G,DTA	1.55	0.4498
	S,T,P,G,DTA	1.49	0.468
S	DTA,S	1.17	0.3526
T	DTA,T	0.7	0.5239

P	DTA,P	16.9	0.0009
G	DTA,G	0.09	0.9139

FGLS Regression Results of STA as Dependent Variable with and Without Moderator for Automobile and Accessories Listed Firms in Nairobi Securities Exchange

As shown in Table 8, results on the effect of financial characteristics on short term debt financing for automobile and accessories listed companies in NSE while operating cash flow was incorporated in the model show that the coefficient of SCF was -0.061 hence firm sizes had a negative impact on short term debt financing when the operating cash flow was incorporated. The p value was 0.000 which is less 5% level of significance. This shows that the moderating influence of operating cash flow on firm size was statistically significant on short term debt financing. The coefficient of TCF was -0.484 hence tangibility had a negative influence on short term debt as operating cash flow increased. The p value was 0.000 which is less than 5% level of significance. This indicates that the moderating influence of operating cash flow on tangibility was statistically significant in debt financing.

The coefficients of PCF and GCF were 0.704 and 0.354 respectively. This indicates that profitability and growth opportunities had a positive influence on short debt respectively when operating cash flow was incorporated. The p values were 0.000 and 0.008 respectively to imply that the moderating influence of operating cash flow on profitability and growth opportunities were significant respectively on short debt financing at 5% level of significance.

To further confirm the influence of the moderator, the coefficients of the model without the moderator are compared with the average marginal effect or change of financial characteristics on short term debt financing. If the two are different then there is moderation else no moderation. The marginal change shows how much short-term debt changes by with an increase in one unit of the relevant financial characteristic when the average moderator value is incorporated. This is achieved by differentiating model 2 in chapter three partially and incorporating the average moderating value as follows

$$\frac{\partial STA_{it}}{\partial T_{it}} = \beta_1 + \beta_6 CF = -0.589 - 0.484 * 0.13 = -0.652$$

$$\frac{\partial STA_{it}}{\partial S_{it}} = \beta_2 + \beta_7 CF = -0.022 - 0.061 * 0.13 = -0.030$$

$$\frac{\partial STA_{it}}{\partial P_{it}} = \beta_3 + \beta_8 CF = 0.178 + 0.704 * 0.13 = 0.270$$

$$\frac{\partial STA_{it}}{\partial G_{it}} = \beta_4 + \beta_9 CF = -0.098 + 0.355 * 0.13 = -0.052$$

Comparison between moderated and non-moderated variables with the operating cash flow revealed that it had a moderating influence on the influence of financial characteristics and short-term leverage of listed automobile and accessories companies.

Table 8 FGLS Regression Results of STA as Dependent Variable with and without Moderator for Automobile and Accessories Listed Companies in Nairobi Securities Exchange

Variable	Without Moderation				With Moderation			
	Coefficient	Std. Error	Z	p>z	Coefficient	Std. Error	Z	p>z
Cons	-.643	.125	5.13	.000	1.118	.221	5.05	.000
T	-.117	.087	-1.36	.175	-.589	.123	-4.81	.000
S	-.006	.007	-.79	.432	-.022	.012	-1.88	.059
P	.273	.125	2.19	.028	.178	.076	2.34	.019
G	.025	.020	1.25	.211	-.098	.036	-2.72	.006
CF					.750	.131	5.74	.000
TCF					-.484	.085	-5.68	.000
SCF					-.061	.013	5.74	.000
PCF					.703	.125	5.64	.000
GCF					.355	.133	2.66	.008
	Wald chi2 (4) =15.02	R2 = 0.5058		P > Chi2 0.0047	Wald chi2 (9) =161.96	R2 = 0.9583		P > Chi2 .0000

FGLS Regression Results of LTA as Dependent Variable with and without Moderator in Automobile and Accessories Companies Listed in Nairobi Securities Exchange

As shown in Table 9, results on the effect of financial characteristics on short term debt financing for automobile and accessories listed companies in NSE while operating cash flow was incorporated in the model show that the coefficient of SCF was -0.016 hence firm sizes had a negative impact on long term debt financing when the operating cash flow was incorporated. The p value was 0.513 which is greater than the 5% level of significance. This shows that the moderating influence of operating cash flow on firm size was statistically non-significant on long term debt financing. The coefficient of TCF was -0.260 hence tangibility had a negative influence on long term debt as operating cash flow increased. The p value was 0.276 which is greater than the 5% level of significance. This indicates that the moderating influence of operating cash flow on tangibility was statistically insignificant on long-debt financing.

The coefficients of PCF and GCF were 0.624 and 0.505 respectively. This indicates that profitability and growth opportunities had a positive influence on long debt respectively when operating cash flow was incorporated. The p values were 0.163 and 0.075 respectively to imply that the moderating influence of operating cash flow on profitability and growth opportunities were insignificant respectively on long debt financing at 5% level of significance.

To further confirm the influence of the moderator, the coefficients of the model without the moderator are compared with the average marginal effect or change of financial characteristics on long term debt financing. If the two are different then there is moderation else no moderation. The marginal change shows how much short-term debt changes by with an increase in one unit of the relevant financial characteristic when the average moderator value is incorporated. This is achieved by differentiating model 2 in chapter three partially and incorporating the average moderating value as follows

$$\frac{\partial STA_{it}}{\partial T_{it}} = \beta_1 + \beta_6 CF = -0.012 - 0.260 * 0.13 = -0.046$$

$$\frac{\partial STA_{it}}{\partial S_{it}} = \beta_2 + \beta_7 CF = -0.0014 - 0.016 * 0.13 = -0.004$$

$$\frac{\partial STA_{it}}{\partial P_{it}} = \beta_3 + \beta_8 CF = -0.233 + 0.624 * 0.13 = 0.315$$

$$\frac{\partial STA_{it}}{\partial G_{it}} = \beta_4 + \beta_9 CF = -0.183 + 0.505 * 0.13 = -0.118$$

Comparison between moderated and non-moderated variables with the operating cash flow revealed that it had a moderating influence on the influence of firm financial characteristics on long term leverage of agricultural listed firms in NSE.

Table 9 FGLS Regression Results of LTA as Dependent Variable with and without Moderator in Automobile and Accessories Firms Listed in Nairobi Securities Exchange

Variable	Without Moderation				With Moderation			
	Coefficient	Std. Error	Z	p>z	Coefficient	Std. Error	Z	p>z
cons	-.004	.191	-.02	.983	.191	.332	.57	.566
T	0.072	0.146	0.49	0.623	-.012	.294	-.04	.966
S	0.006	0.0109	0.51	0.608	-.001	.016	-.08	.932
P	-0.193	.224	-.86	.390	-.233	.233	-1	.316
G	-.037	.025	-1.47	.142	-.183	.079	-2.32	.02
CF					.094	.277	.34	.731
TCF					-.260	.239	-1.09	.276
SCF					-.016	.025	-.65	.513
PCF					.624	.447	1.39	.163
GCF					.505	.284	1.78	.075
	Wald chi ² (4) =6.03	R ² = 0.2316	P > Chi ² 0.1968	Wald chi ² (9) = 31.44	R ² = 0.5671	p>Chi ² .0000		

4.36.20 FGLS Regression Results of DTA as Dependent Variable with and without Moderator in Automobile and Accessories Firms Listed in Nairobi Securities Exchange

As shown in Table 10, results on the effect of financial characteristics on debt financing for automobile and accessories listed companies in NSE while operating cash flow was incorporated in the model show that the coefficient of SCF was -0.005 hence firm sizes had a negative influence on debt financing when the operating cash flow was incorporated. The p value was 0.847 which is greater than the 5% level of significance. This shows that the moderating influence of operating cash flow on firm size was statistically insignificant on debt financing. The coefficient of TCF was -0.015 hence tangibility had a negative influence on debt as operating cash flow increased. The p value was 0.935 which is greater than the 5% level of significance. This indicates that the moderating influence of operating cash flow on tangibility was statistically insignificant on debt financing.

The coefficients of PCF and GCF were -0.357 and -0.054 respectively. This indicates that profitability and growth opportunities had an inverse influence on debt respectively when operating cash flow was incorporated. The p values were 0.473 and 0.748 respectively to imply that the moderating influence of operating cash flow on profitability and growth opportunities were insignificant on debt financing at 5% level of significance.

To further confirm the influence of the moderator, the coefficients of the model without the moderator are compared with the average marginal effect or change of financial characteristics on debt financing. If the two

are different then there is moderation else no moderation. The marginal change shows how much debt changes by with an increase in one unit of the relevant financial characteristic when the average moderator value is incorporated. This is achieved by differentiating model 2 in chapter three partially and incorporating the average moderating value as follows

$$\frac{\partial STA_{it}}{\partial Tit} = \beta_1 + \beta_6 CF = -0.259 - 0.015 * 0.13 = -0.261$$

$$\frac{\partial STA_{it}}{\partial Sit} = \beta_2 + \beta_7 CF = -0.013 - 0.005 * 0.13 = -0.014$$

$$\frac{\partial STA_{it}}{\partial Pit} = \beta_3 + \beta_8 CF = 0.357 - 0.018 * 0.13 = 0.355$$

$$\frac{\partial STA_{it}}{\partial Git} = \beta_4 + \beta_9 CF = -0.047 - 0.054 * 0.13 = 0.054$$

Comparison between moderated and non-moderated variables with the operating cash flow revealed that it had a moderating influence on the influence of firm financial characteristics on the leverage of automobile and accessories listed firm in NSE.

Table 10 FGLS Regression Results of DTA as Dependent Variable with Moderator in Automobile and Accessories Companies Listed in Nairobi Securities Exchange

Variable	Without Moderation				With Moderation			
	Coefficient	Std. Error	Z	p>z	Coefficient	Std. Error	Z	p>z
cons	0.725	0.216	3.35	.001	.905	.464	1.95	.051
T	-.112	.164	-.68	.496	-.259	.309	-.84	.402
S	-.004	.012	-.37	.714	-.013	0.025	-.52	.604
P	-.052	.247	-.21	.833	-.018	.258	-.07	.944
G	-.013	.026	-.49	.626	-.007	.043	-.16	.874
CF					.059	.320	.180	.855
TCF					-.015	.188	-.08	.935
SCF					-.005	.026	-.18	.857
PCF					.357	.497	.72	.473
GCF					-.054	.167	-.32	.748
	Wald chi ² (4) =0.53	R ² = 0.0839		P > Chi ² 0.9701	Wald chi ² (9) = 1.63	R ² = .166 4		p>Chi ² .966

Conclusion and Recommendations

There is a need to evaluate customer development strategies and types of customer who are seeking goods and services from listed automobile and accessories companies. Since debt capital is dependent on the ability of the firm to repay back there is a need for listed non-financial companies to venture into markets which are not only profitable but also sustainable. This can only be achieved through adopted of real time data management strategies amongst all non-financial listed companies.

Further, listed automobile and accessories companies ought to evaluate their working capital management strategies since an increase in profitability was associated with increased short-term debt. This consistency was not retained throughout the period under investigation. This implies that though companies were profitable in a single accounting cycle similar trends were not sustainable in subsequent accounting periods. This call for forensic examination of accounting records to minimize possibilities of window dressing their accounting

records. It was paramount to note that even though profitability had a positive effect on leverage it was not significant. This calls for an examination of leverage policy by listed non-financial companies to ensure that leverage financing matches profitability targets.

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